

UDC 66.097

APPLICATION OF MATHEMATICAL MODELING IN THE PROCESS OF HYDROTREATING VACUUM GAS OIL

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Abstract: *In this paper, the process of hydrotreating vacuum gas oil using mathematical modeling methods is considered. Hydrotreating is a key stage in the processing of heavy oil fractions, aimed at removing sulfur-containing compounds, nitrogen and oxygen-containing impurities, as well as improving the quality of the resulting petroleum products.*

Keywords: *hydrotreating, vacuum gas oil, forecasting, mathematical model, analysis, fractional composition.*

The oil refining and petrochemical industry plays an important, and in some cases, the most important role in the economy of any country. There is a steady increase in gasoline consumption in the world, and recently the consumption of diesel fuel has been especially intense. Motor fuels are currently produced almost exclusively from oil and gas condensate [1].

The urgency of deepening oil refining is increasing due to a decrease in oil production growth, an increase in production and transportation costs. The limited reserves of "traditional oil" lead to the need to involve heavy and bitumen oils in the processing [2].

The current level of development of scientific research and technological processes makes it possible to obtain a wide range of commercial petroleum products from oil residues, as well as valuable carbon products based on high-quality petroleum coke. The leading role in solving this problem is assigned to hydrogen catalytic processes, which make it possible to prepare oil residues for further processing by demetallization, sulfur removal and hydrogen saturation [3].

Consequently, catalytic and hydrogenation processes are becoming increasingly important, which make it possible to obtain high-quality components of motor fuels from high-boiling petroleum raw materials. One of the most important processes for the oil refining industry is catalytic cracking [4-7]. The raw material of this process is vacuum gas oil, a fraction with a boiling point (350-550 °C) containing a large number of sulfur, nitrogen, oxygen compounds, as well as organometallic substances.

Vacuum gas oils are the main raw materials for catalytic cracking and hydrocracking plants, which produce large amounts of high—octane gasoline and distillates, which are components of commercial diesel fuels. As a rule, vacuum gas oil contains at least 2% by weight. sulfur, therefore, the motor fuels obtained from it, are also characterized by its high content. This can be avoided by means of preliminary deep hydrotreating of vacuum gas oil on catalysts specially developed for this process [8–16]. As a result of this process, preliminary upgrading of the feedstock is achieved by removal of heteroatomic and organometallic substances, as well as by hydrogenation of unsaturated compounds and, partially, polycyclic aromatic compounds in a hydrogen medium on catalysts [17]. Thus, preliminary hydrotreating of vacuum gas oil also makes it possible to solve the problem of improving the quality of fuel fractions (gasoline and medium distillates), which are subsequently used for compounding motor fuels. On the other hand, model development is complicated by the fact that catalytic processes, including hydrotreating, are complex multicomponent systems in which a large number of different reactions take place.

The hydrotreating technology was implemented as part of the KT-1/1 deep fuel oil processing unit at the S-100 section of one of the refineries of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Vacuum distillate from a mixture of paraffin Kazakh and West Siberian oil is used as the raw material of the hydrotreating process. The process of preliminary hydrotreating of vacuum gas oil is carried out at a high temperature of 350-400 °C and a pressure of 4-5 MPa in a hydrogen medium using a bifunctional catalyst. Hydrotreating of raw materials is carried out in two parallel operating reactors with a stationary catalyst layer. The gas phase of the reactor contains: hydrogen-containing gas (H₂ concentration of at least 90%), hydrogen sulfide and ammonia; in the liquid– a mixture of C₁₅+ hydrocarbons, and in the solid, a heterogeneous Al-Co-Mo catalyst.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the vacuum gas oil hydrotreating process: R-1 and R-2 reactors; S-1 and S-2 are high and low pressure separators, respectively; E-1 – pre-evaporation vessel; K-1 – stabilization column; K-2 – stripping column; S-3 is a reflux tank.

Most of the reactions occurring in the hydrotreating reactor are exothermic. The process of refining raw materials is based on chemical reactions that facilitate the fractional composition and improve the quality of products. Sulfur compounds, which are part of the component composition of petroleum products, adversely affect the quality of the distillates obtained and the service life of the devices, therefore, the need for hydrodesulfurization is obvious. Sulfur-containing compounds include mercaptans, sulfides and disulfides, thiophanes and thiophenes. Currently, the chemistry of the hydrodesulfurization process has been studied. Under hydrotreating conditions, mercaptans and sulfides are primarily desulfurized, followed by thiophenes and benzothiophenes.

The presence of a large number of individual components in the reaction mixture and a multitude of ongoing reactions makes it difficult to develop a mathematical model of the process due to the inability to quickly and accurately identify each of the substances and the cumbersomeness of the kinetic model obtained in this way. Therefore, various simplifications based on the aggregation of individual reagents and individual reactions into pseudoreagents and groups of reactions, respectively, are used to solve this problem [18].

Table 1 – Results of laboratory studies of unstable gasoline and diesel fraction obtained during the hydrotreating process

Indicators	Diesel fuel	Unstable gasoline
Sulfur content, wt. %	0,015–0,023	0,101–0,182
Kinematic viscosity at 20 °C, mm ² /s	3,709–7,603	0,796–0,871

Dynamic viscosity at 20 °C, MPa·s	3,105–6,529	0,584–0,643
Density at 20 °C, g/cm ³	0,837–0,859	0,733–0,738
Molar mass, g/mol	183–209	99–105

To determine the key components involved in chemical transformations during the hydrotreating of vacuum gas oil, an analysis of the composition and properties of raw materials and products was carried out. Most studies of the hydrotreating process are based on laboratory experiments, the results of laboratory studies of vacuum gas oil before and after the hydrotreating process, see (Table 1). The following methods and instruments were used: cryoscopy method on the KRION-1 apparatus for determining the molecular weight of substances; Stabinger SVM3000 viscometer (Anton Paar) for measuring the density, dynamic and kinematic viscosity of samples; SPECTROSCAN S X-ray energy dispersion analyzer for measuring the mass fraction of sulfur in petroleum fractions (Table – 1).

Based on the data obtained on the composition and properties of raw materials and products, a formalized scheme is being developed that will reflect the main chemical transformations of pseudocomponents in the industrial hydrotreating process.

Therefore, it is relevant to use the mathematical modeling method [19, 20], which allows not only to offset the production costs of conducting experimental runs, both in monetary and time terms, but also to predict the conditions of the hydrotreating process, the composition and properties of the products obtained.

The use of a mathematical model of the vacuum gas oil hydrotreating process will further determine the optimal values of production parameters to ensure the required degree of purification of raw materials without overheating the catalyst.

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